

Functional Approach to the Problem of Origin of Life— Photochemical Splitting of Water and Reduction of Nitrogen and Carbon dioxide

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Jeewanu, the protocells, synthesised by the action of light on sterilised aqueous mixtures of simple organic and inorganic substances have many of the properties of biological order. Ammonium molybdate *Jeewanu* and thiocyanate *Jeewanu* are characteristic in their ability of splitting of water molecule in sunlight and of fixation of inorganic carbon and nitrogen. Unlike the many minerals which are extensively used at present for photochemical splitting of water, *Jeewanu* needs a night dark phase for reviving its ability to split water molecule and to reduce inorganic carbon. Both these processes need *Jeewanu* structure whereas nitrogen fixation can be affected even with materials left over after the breakdown of *Jeewanu*. The photobiological like splitting of water by *Jeewanu* may be exploited for utilising solar energy for fixation of inorganic carbon and molecular nitrogen.

THE most important work utilising sunlight as the means of increasing the soil nitrogen is the investigations of Professor N. R. Dhar¹ and is being carried out for the last four decades. For the production of artificial nitrogenous manure a cheap source of hydrogen is needed and this is hydrogen from water, but water needs about 68 K cal per mole energy for its breaking up into hydrogen and oxygen.

To find a way out of the energy crisis, an understanding of the processes that took place during the period when life forms were originating is necessary. Abelson's view² is that the secondary atmosphere in which life originated consisted of N₂, CO₂ and H₂O. Sillen³ and Rutten⁴, as a result of equilibrium calculations, came to the conclusion that "equilibrium conditions seem to exclude the formation of the 'thin soup' in the normal oceanic conditions even under an anoxygenic atmosphere". Perhaps there was an acute shortage of organic carbon in the hydrosphere when life came into existence. The only possible way life could originate on the earth was that the earliest living systems had the ability to split water to hydrogen and oxygen deriving the energy from sunlight and to utilise the proton thus set free for the reduction of N₂ or CO₂ to ammoniacal nitrogen and organic material.

The plants utilise radiations between 400 and 700 nm, which is photosynthetically active radiation (PAR).

This PAR is 50% of the total sunlight and on earth's surface has an intensity of 800–100 W/m². The energy needed to break water to hydrogen and oxygen is 68.3 K cal per gm mole, and this must be absorbed by the water to produce every mole of hydrogen. Since water is transparent to visible solar radiation from 350 to 750 nm and does not absorb light greater than $\lambda > 200$ nm, direct decomposition of water by solar radiation is not possible and the process needs sensitizers and/or catalysts. Many redox-dyes and pigments have been reported in the liberation which act as sensitizers in photooxidation and photoreduction of water. In plants, photosynthesis is carried out by the chloroplasts where photolysis of water is carried out by the concerted action of chlorophyll which absorbs the protons and the Mn-enzyme of photosystem II which acts as charge storage catalyst. The synthesis of ATP and NADPH₂ occurs and these are the two components needed for the reduction of CO₂ to carbohydrate.

In vitro system containing chloroplast-ferredoxin-hydrogenase, on illumination causes the liberation of oxygen and hydrogen. The protons liberated at photosystem II are converted to hydrogen molecules by the hydrogenase. Benemann *et al* in 1973 suggested the possibility of using this system for commercial production of hydrogen⁵. The idea was later developed by Hall's school⁶.

Solar energy has been converted to chemical energy using heterogeneous photocatalytic reactions and thus chemical compounds synthesised^{7,8}.

Photogenerated carriers, electrons and holes, in the space charge layer of a semiconductor electrode can be transferred to the reactants in an electrolyte solution and cause the photo-assisted decomposition or synthesis of chemical compounds^{9,10}. Semiconductor catalysts may be assumed to undergo charge transfer across a solid-liquid junction similar to that in semiconductor electrodes, i.e., charge transfer between semiconductor and redox reagents in solution would take the form of a conductance band and a valence band.

Functional properties of Jeewanu: With the above background of the work on photochemical splitting of water and reduction of N₂ and CO₂ by inorganic catalysts, the *Jeewanu* particles were examined because these have several properties of biological order and in all probability particles like these were immediate precursors of cellular life. In photobiological splitting of water into hydrogen and oxygen ferredoxin plays an important role of electron transfer and it is observed in several algae.

The work on *Jeewanu* was published in 1963^{11,12} and independently confirmed by Briggs in 1964¹³ and again in 1965¹⁴. In 1980 it was reported that *Jeewanu* have ability of splitting water molecule in sunlight and also of photochemical fixation of nitrogen and carbon dioxide by the photolysis of water¹⁵.

Jeewanu, produced by the action of sunlight on sterilised aqueous mixture containing ammonium molybdate, diammonium hydrogen phosphate, biological minerals and formaldehyde have properties of growth, multiplication and metabolic activity^{11,12}. Elemental analysis of *Jeewanu* indicated that it contains C, 13.87; H, 2.87; N, 9.22; Mo, 39.21 and P, 2.21%¹⁶. *Jeewanu* contain other elements as Fe, 0.18; Mn, 0.005; Mg and K 0.003; Ca, 0.006 and Na, 0.10%¹⁷. These particles have a boundary wall and internal structures^{18,19}. They can be fixed with biological fixatives, stained with biological dyes²⁰ and have many of the biochemicals of the cells such as amino acids in free form and peptide combinations, nucleic acid bases and nucleosides^{20,21}, phospholipids²², a number of sugars such as glucose, fructose, ribose, deoxyribose²³ and a number of organic acids. These particles have material with esterase, catalase^{13,14}, phosphatase, ATPase, urease and peroxidase like activities¹⁶ and are sensitive to the presence of antibiotics in the environment^{24,25}.

As ferredoxin has been found in all the cells, *Jeewanu* were tested for the presence of ferredoxin-like material in them with positive results^{26,28}.

The two constituents of nitrogenase are one, a Fe-S-protein and the other, a Mo-Fe-S-protein. If Fe-S-protein function could be performed by the ferredoxin-like material of *Jeewanu* and a large concentration of molybdenum could form a material similar in action to Mo-Fe-S-protein part

of nitrogenase, perhaps *Jeewanu* could fix molecular nitrogen and show the properties of nitrogenase-like material. With this understanding a search for nitrogenase-like activity in *Jeewanu* was undertaken. It was found that *Jeewanu* and water mixture, on irradiation with light from Xenon lamp, showed the conversion of acetylene in the overhead space of the irradiated mixture to ethylene. It was further observed that if D₂O is used instead of H₂O, the ethylene formed is CHD=CHD indicating that it is the proton from H₂O which reduced CH≡CH to CH₂=CH₂²⁹.

It was observed that if purified CO₂ is bubbled through a mixture of *Jeewanu* and water while it is exposed to sunlight a part of CO₂ is converted to unsaturated hydrocarbon³⁰ and some of it is converted to organic material soluble in the irradiated mixture. A night phase is needed for the reactivation of the particles next day (Table 1). Similarly, it was observed that if bicarbonate is used as the source of inorganic carbon *Jeewanu* are able to convert it to organic material on exposure to sunlight in aqueous mixture. Optimum fixation is obtained when the conc. of NaHCO₃ per ml of distilled water is 5 mg and *Jeewanu* 1 mg and the air, freed of CO₂ and O₂ by passing through pyrogallol and caustic soda solution, is gradually passed through the irradiated mixtures. Fixation of nitrogen is also observed and a part of the nitrogen of the overhead is converted to fixed nitrogen. This nitrogen fixation is not affected by varying the concentrations of bicarbonate in the irradiation mixtures. There is a slight decrease in nitrogen fixation in all the flasks having NaHCO₃ but this decrease is the same at all the concentrations of NaHCO₃ (Table 2).

TABLE 1—MILLILITRES OF 0.001 N KMnO₄ SOLUTION NEEDED FOR THE NEUTRALISATION OF UNSATURATED HYDROCARBONS FORMED IN 50 ml DISTILLED WATER, TRAPPING EVOLVED GASES FROM THE IRRADIATED MIXTURE OF *Jeewanu*, ON PASSING CO₂ THROUGH IT

Exposure days	Exposure time (in hours)						
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	2.05	5.00	6.70	7.00	6.10	5.50	5.00
2	2.05	5.40	5.85	7.15	6.75	5.95	5.00
3	2.05	6.10	7.05	6.66	6.30	6.35	5.00
4	2.05	5.70	7.00	6.35	5.90	4.85	4.75
5	2.05	5.50	6.05	5.50	5.15	4.45	4.00
6	2.05	4.20	4.75	4.00	3.40	3.40	3.10
7	2.05	4.00	4.25	4.00	3.40	3.15	3.00
8	2.05	3.80	3.85	3.50	3.20	2.65	2.55
9	2.05	3.25	3.35	3.00	3.00	2.45	2.10
10	2.05	2.85	3.00	2.70	2.50	2.20	2.05
11	2.05	2.45	2.65	2.30	2.15	2.05	2.05
12	2.05	2.10	2.15	2.05	2.05	2.05	2.05

AMOUNT OF ORGANIC CARBON (mg) FORMED PER 2.0 ml OF IRRADIATED MIXTURE HAVING *Jeewanu* ON PASSING CO₂ THROUGH IT, FOR 6 hr OF EXPOSURE TO SUNLIGHT IN A DAY

Amount of organic carbon (mg)	Exposure time (days)						
	0	2	4	6	8	10	12
	0.205	0.306	0.383	0.434	0.485	0.510	0.536

TABLE 2—ORGANIC CARBON (mg) FORMED PHOTOCHEMICALLY BY 2.0 ml OF *Jeewanu* MIXTURES HAVING DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF NaHCO₃

Amount of NaHCO ₃ per 100 ml of the mixture (mg)	Exposure time (hours)							
	0	6	12	18	24	30	36	42
Control	0.178	0.180	0.180	0.183	0.183	0.183	0.185	0.185
50	0.178	0.196	0.215	0.228	0.236	0.244	0.251	0.256
100	0.180	0.205	0.229	0.246	0.257	0.267	0.276	0.281
500	0.183	0.236	0.308	0.357	0.397	0.434	0.464	0.482
750	0.185	0.231	0.295	0.333	0.366	0.401	0.431	0.451
1000	0.187	0.215	0.241	0.262	0.281	0.294	0.305	0.317

AMINO NITROGEN (mg) FORMED PHOTOCHEMICALLY BY 2.0 ml OF *Jeewanu* MIXTURES HAVING DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF NaHCO₃

Amount of NaHCO ₃ per 100 ml of the mixture (mg)	Exposure time (hours)							
	0	6	12	18	24	30	36	42
Control	0.171	0.222	0.257	0.299	0.339	0.367	0.390	0.415
50	0.171	0.219	0.253	0.293	0.322	0.347	0.374	0.402
100	0.171	0.217	0.253	0.290	0.321	0.344	0.371	0.399
500	0.172	0.217	0.251	0.285	0.312	0.366	0.360	0.381
750	0.172	0.217	0.250	0.281	0.306	0.324	0.343	0.362
1000	0.172	0.217	0.250	0.274	0.296	0.318	0.341	0.361

The above results show that fixation of CO₂ and nitrogen are effected by two different sets of enzymes after hydrogen is made available by the splitting of water. Further investigations revealed that in the fixation of CO₂ the structure of *Jeewanu* is important and once the structure is destroyed completely the fixation of CO₂ stops. For the fixation of nitrogen no structure is needed and it can proceed even when the structure of *Jeewanu* is completely destroyed leaving only the chemical constituents in the irradiation mixture.

The work on fixation of HCO₃⁻ carbon was repeated using H¹⁴CO₃⁻ and it was observed that ¹⁴C is present in the organic material formed in the irradiated mixture²⁹.

Investigation of the photolytic splitting of water by *Jeewanu* alone was undertaken. It was observed that if a mixture of *Jeewanu* and water is thoroughly shaken and exposed to sunlight, bubbles of gas start coming out of the mixture after about 10 to 15 min. The liberation of gas continues for about 1 hr. The bubbles of gas come out from the bottom of the tube where the particles settle down. If sunlight is cut off the liberation of gas bubbles stops.

Our first reaction was that the liberated gas may be the dissolved air in the mixture which came out of the mixture when it became warm due to the heat of the sunlight if these *Jeewanu* have an extraordinary property of absorbing a lot of air. So after the mixture stopped giving out gas bubbles after about 1 hr of sunlight exposure, it was cooled to room temperature, thoroughly shaken to provide the condition for optimum absorption of air by the particles and exposed. Another crop of gas bubbles was obtained. However, when the liberation of gas

stopped again after the next hour, the process of cooling, shaking and exposure was repeated. It was found that only a few gas bubbles come out the third time and that too for a short while. On repeating this process several times the same day, it was observed that the particles stopped giving out gas bubbles though optimum condition for the absorption of air by the particles was provided each time. This indicates that the gas bubbles which come out of the particles on exposure to sunlight are not of the dissolved or adsorbed air. Moreover, a control mixture which did not have *Jeewanu* but other inorganic solids did not show any liberation of gas. This showed that *Jeewanu* have the property of splitting water.

The *Jeewanu*, after about a few times of cooling, shaking and exposure, were in capable of gas liberation on that particular day. When these *Jeewanu* rendered inactive after a few times of cooling, shaking and exposure to sunlight on a single day, are allowed to stand overnight in the dark, they become active again for the liberation of gas (Table 3).

In another experiment two similar mixtures were prepared and their ability to liberate gas was exhausted by repeated cooling, shaking and exposure to sunlight. One mixture was then kept in the dark through the night and the other one was allowed to stand 1 meter away from a 1000 watts tungsten filament lamp through the whole night. It was observed the next morning that the mixture kept in the dark during the night had recovered and showed liberation of gas on exposure to sunlight but the mixture kept in light during the night had not. This indicated that a dark phase is essential for the reactivation of the *Jeewanu*.

It was further observed that if the *Jeewanu* are not shaken at all and are kept for exposure in sunlight after the night phase there is very little evolution of gas bubbles and during shaking after night some gas comes out of the mixture. It therefore appears that some transformation takes place in *Jeewanu* in the night and some gas is liberated but due to the contact of this gas with the particle an equilibrium sets in. This gas is driven out during shaking and creates conditions favourable for the splitting of water by *Jeewanu* in sunlight. Shaking during the day may also be doing the same in addition to bringing newer surface of *Jeewanu* in contact with light and splitting of water molecules takes place. It stops after some time when the surface of the particle in contact with light is rendered useless for the reaction. This surface is reactivated next day after the dark phase.

Manometric experiments using Warburg's flask: The experiments were then performed with Warburg's flasks. Three similar Warburg's flasks of total volume 14.5 ml each were taken and their manometers were filled with mercury. The first flask had 5 ml distilled water in the main vessel and 0.3 ml distilled water in the side arm; this acted as the control. The second flask had 5 ml distilled water and 10 mg *Jeewanu* in the main vessel and

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TABLE 3 - LIBERATION OF GAS BUBBLES PER MINUTE ON EXPOSURE OF THE MIXTURE TO SUNLIGHT BY HIGH MINERAL *Jeewanu*

		Number of gas bubbles (Arithmetic mean and statistical average)					
		Exposure time (minutes)					
		10	20	30	40	50	60
1st day		14.8 ± 1.98	27.6 ± 2.37	17.6 ± 1.16	15.0 ± 1.14	15.2 ± 0.86	15.4 ± 1.43
		3.0 ± 0.31	30.8 ± 1.35	24.4 ± 1.69	18.8 ± 0.55	12.6 ± 0.56	10.6 ± 0.50
		14.8 ± 1.01	20.0 ± 0.74	17.2 ± 0.73	11.4 ± 1.02	8.6 ± 1.28	6.6 ± 0.50
		0.6 ± 0.39	9.6 ± 0.81	3.4 ± 0.24	7.2 ± 0.37	7.2 ± 0.37	1.6 ± 0.4
2nd day		0.0 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.2	0.4 ± 0.24	0.2 ± 0.2	0.2 ± 0.2	0.0 ± 0.0
		16.4 ± 0.68	26.2 ± 0.58	26.4 ± 2.42	18.0 ± 1.04	17.2 ± 1.04	16.0 ± 1.71
		39.8 ± 2.11	56.0 ± 0.70	38.2 ± 1.28	33.6 ± 0.50	28.2 ± 1.0	22.0 ± 0.70
		1.4 ± 0.20	4.4 ± 0.81	4.2 ± 0.69	2.2 ± 0.2	0.6 ± 0.39	0.2 ± 0.2
3rd day		20.0 ± 0.70	38.4 ± 1.31	34.8 ± 0.80	30.6 ± 0.60	19.2 ± 1.2	16.0 ± 0.7
		0.0 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.2	0.2 ± 0.2	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0
		14.4 ± 0.67	36.0 ± 1.07	24.2 ± 1.15	26.0 ± 1.88	16.6 ± 0.50	15.2 ± 1.15
		61.4 ± 2.56	55.6 ± 1.29	40.6 ± 2.10	30.4 ± 1.35	28.4 ± 1.50	18.6 ± 3.16
4th day		3.0 ± 0.31	17.2 ± 1.83	11.6 ± 0.67	11.4 ± 0.50	8.8 ± 0.37	17.8 ± 0.96
		0.4 ± 0.24	4.4 ± 0.60	2.6 ± 0.67	1.6 ± 0.67	0.6 ± 0.39	0.2 ± 0.2
		0.0 ± 0.0	0.4 ± 0.24	0.2 ± 0.2	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0
		18.6 ± 0.93	34.8 ± 1.52	32.0 ± 1.30	20.2 ± 0.80	16.6 ± 1.12	9.0 ± 0.83
5th days		50.4 ± 1.43	57.2 ± 1.15	21.0 ± 1.41	16.0 ± 0.83	9.2 ± 0.96	5.0 ± 0.37
		8.0 ± 0.44	12.8 ± 0.73	10.0 ± 1.22	6.4 ± 0.67	4.8 ± 0.33	3.6 ± 0.43
		15.8 ± 0.86	34.8 ± 1.24	30.8 ± 2.04	21.2 ± 1.11	10.2 ± 0.96	4.6 ± 0.50
		0.0 ± 0.0	1.2 ± 0.37	4.8 ± 0.58	2.4 ± 0.50	1.4 ± 0.24	0.6 ± 0.39
6th day		26.0 ± 0.70	42.2 ± 1.39	23.4 ± 0.50	17.8 ± 1.01	10.8 ± 0.58	5.4 ± 0.50
		0.8 ± 0.37	1.8 ± 0.37	2.8 ± 0.37	3.0 ± 0.44	1.6 ± 0.40	0.8 ± 0.37
		12.6 ± 0.93	35.0 ± 1.34	19.8 ± 1.65	17.4 ± 1.02	11.4 ± 1.36	9.6 ± 0.68
		12.0 ± 1.41	26.6 ± 1.12	19.2 ± 1.35	7.6 ± 0.86	5.2 ± 1.15	4.4 ± 0.81
7th day		15.0 ± 0.70	16.8 ± 0.58	8.6 ± 0.52	5.8 ± 0.48	6.2 ± 0.58	4.4 ± 0.24
		13.6 ± 0.68	13.0 ± 0.50	6.2 ± 0.73	3.0 ± 0.44	1.2 ± 0.20	1.4 ± 0.24
		0.0 ± 0.0	2.2 ± 0.58	3.6 ± 0.40	3.0 ± 0.31	1.8 ± 0.37	0.6 ± 0.39
		0.0 ± 0.0	0.4 ± 0.24	0.0 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.2	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0
8th day		20.8 ± 1.24	22.4 ± 1.28	17.2 ± 0.86	7.8 ± 0.88	6.6 ± 0.24	6.8 ± 0.86
		4.0 ± 0.54	3.6 ± 0.97	5.0 ± 0.83	3.8 ± 0.58	2.6 ± 0.58	1.2 ± 0.58
		21.8 ± 1.59	18.2 ± 1.06	10.6 ± 0.50	8.0 ± 0.59	8.4 ± 0.50	5.6 ± 0.50
		7.6 ± 0.92	5.0 ± 1.09	2.4 ± 0.24	0.4 ± 0.24	0.4 ± 0.24	0.2 ± 0.24
9th day		10.4 ± 0.81	6.0 ± 0.54	3.4 ± 0.24	2.6 ± 0.24	1.6 ± 0.28	0.6 ± 0.39
		5.2 ± 0.58	4.4 ± 0.68	0.4 ± 0.24	0.2 ± 0.20	0.0 ± 0.00	0.0 ± 0.0
		0.2 ± 0.2	4.2 ± 0.48	3.2 ± 0.24	2.6 ± 0.24	1.4 ± 0.24	0.8 ± 0.2
		0.0 ± 0.0	0.4 ± 0.24	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0

LIBERATION OF GAS BUBBLES PER MINUTE ON EXPOSURE OF THE MIXTURE TO SUNLIGHT. AFTER EXPOSURE FOR 4 DAYS, AFTER 5 TIMES OF COOLING AND SHAKING EACH DAY. ONE MIXTURE WAS KEPT UNDER 1000 WATTS LAMP DURING NIGHT WHEREAS A SIMILAR MIXTURE WAS KEPT IN DARK DURING NIGHT

Number of gas bubbles (Arithmetic mean and statistical average)

D - mixture stored in dark during night.
L - mixture stored in light during night.

0.3 ml distilled water in the side arm. The third flask had 5 ml distilled water and 10 mg *Jeewanu* in the main vessel and 0.3 ml alkaline pyrogallol solution in the side arm. This was to absorb oxygen of the flask. This third flask was allowed to stand in the room to allow the oxygen of the flask to be absorbed by pyrogallol. When sufficient absorption of oxygen took place, the tap of the manometer was opened to allow that volume of air to come in. After several such treatments, all the oxygen of the flask was completely absorbed and the manometer showed no difference in pressure. All the three Warburg's flasks with attached manometer were then fixed in a stand keeping them as close to each other as possible so that the temperature of all the three was the same during the experiment, and the whole unit was exposed to light. The side lobes of all the flasks were covered with black cloth to avoid photochemical decomposition of the alkaline pyrogallol and also to provide similar conditions in all the three sets. The manometer reading of the control was subtracted from the readings of the other two to account for changes due to fluctuations in temperature.

It was observed that on exposure to sunlight there was increase in pressure of both the flasks containing *Jeewanu* and water and the increase was more in the flask which had pyrogallol in the side arm. After about 1 hr the pressure increase stopped. The whole unit was then transferred to shade. There was rapid decrease in pressure in both the *Jeewanu* containing flasks and the decrease was more in the flask with alkaline pyrogallol in the side arm. This decrease in pressure also became slow and stopped after about 1 hr. When the whole unit was again exposed to sunlight the pressure increase in *Jeewanu* containing flasks was observed and when again put in shade, after one hour, a decrease in pressure was recorded. This processes could be repeated a few times each day and by the end there was considerable decrease in the pressure when the unit was exposed to light. Next day after the dark phase of the night the reaction started afresh.

In light, the water molecules break-up into hydrogen and oxygen. The hydrogen set free combines with the nitrogen of the overhead space of the flask and the oxygen is absorbed in the alkaline pyrogallol in the side arm. The water splitting reaction is light dependent whereas the combination of N_2 and H_2 is not. Both the reactions, however, are hindered by the presence of oxygen in the overhead space. When *Jeewanu* and water mixture is exposed to light both the reactions start. When the flasks are brought in shade, the splitting of water stops but the combination of nitrogen of the overhead space with hydrogen produced during exposure continues so long as hydrogen is present in the flask. This accounts for the decrease in the pressure of the flask in shade. After all the free hydrogen of the flask is consumed the reaction of N_2 and H_2 also stops and decrease in the pressure in shade also stops.

Of the several types of *Jeewanu* which have been prepared and their water splitting property in sun-

light investigated, two types are important: one, which is formed by the action of light on sterilised aqueous mixture of ammonium molybdate, diammonium hydrogen phosphate, biological minerals and formaldehyde and are known as ammonium molybdate *Jeewanu*¹⁶ and the other, which is produced by the interaction of ammonium thiocyanate, calcium acetate, potassium hydrogen phosphate, biological minerals and formaldehyde and are called thiocyanate *Jeewanu*²². The effect of different metallic ions as Mo, Mn, Co, Cu and Zn in the parental medium of thiocyanate *Jeewanu* on the water splitting ability of the *Jeewanu* has been investigated. Co has been found to appreciably accelerate the water splitting ability.

The ammonium molybdate *Jeewanu* have greater ability of splitting water in sunlight. It has been observed that if acetic acid is also used as a source of organic carbon in ammonium molybdate *Jeewanu* parental medium together with formaldehyde, *Jeewanu* produced in it have greater water splitting ability. This ability can also be accelerated by incorporating more minerals in the *Jeewanu* by increasing the mineral solution in the parental medium. If a large volume of biological minerals are added in the parental medium to begin with, the formation of *Jeewanu* is considerably hindered or can even be stopped with large excess of mineral solution in the parental medium of *Jeewanu*¹⁶. However, if the parental medium of *Jeewanu* is initially started with the usual necessary amount of biological minerals and after 1 hr of exposure, when some *Jeewanu* are already formed in the mixture, additional mineral solution is added, the particles formed on further exposure are a little less than the control in dry weight but have greater ability of splitting water.

On studying the effect of period of exposure of the parental mixture of *Jeewanu* to sunlight on the water splitting of *Jeewanu* it has been observed that this increases with increasing period of exposure of the parental mixture to a certain limit. Further exposure destroys this ability. The effect of storing *Jeewanu* in their parental environmental medium in wet condition, and in dry condition in contact with air or under dry anaerobic conditions has been studied and it has been observed that *Jeewanu* are best preserved in their parental environmental medium and then comes preservation of *Jeewanu* in dry condition under anaerobic condition. Freshly prepared *Jeewanu* are more active in splitting water and this ability starts decreasing after 8 to 10 days and remains only in traces after 18 days.

Studying the effect of pH it has been observed that best gas evolution is observed in phosphate buffer at pH 8. The effect of pH on the fixation of inorganic carbon and molecular nitrogen by *Jeewanu* has also been studied.

Jeewanu as precursors of cellular life: The most interesting part is that *Jeewanu* have properties of biological order. They grow from within, multiply by budding and have metabolic activity. They can adapt and thus evolve in mildly changing

environment. Confirming the work on *Jeewanu*, Dr. M. H. Briggs wrote¹⁴ :

"While the definition of 'life' and 'living' is a difficult problem, it can be said that these microscopic objects (*Jeewanu*) satisfy many of the criteria of living cells. It seems entirely probable that objects similar to those observed in the present experiments were formed in the oceans of the primitive Earth and were the immediate precursor of cellular life".

Jeewanu are quite different from coacervates of Oparin²¹, microspheres of Fox²² and marigranules of Egami²³ which are photochemically inert. It appears that the secondary atmosphere of the earth in which life originated consisted of N₂, CO₂, and H₂O² and not of CH₄, NH₃, H₂, and H₂O as earlier believed²⁴. In the absence of hydrogen the atmosphere of CO₂, N₂, and H₂ was energy poor. There are also evidences to suggest that there was very little organic matter in the hydrosphere of the earth when life originated, what to say of the possibility of the 'primordial soup' of Haldane. Even at that time a number of inorganic catalysts and semiconductor surfaces were effecting water splitting utilising the energy of sunlight. The properties of these minerals were greatly modified and they became more effective in photochemical splitting of water when they came in contact with the organic material synthesised.

Nature's self-organising process was in operation^{25,26} and cybernetics and feed back mechanism produced such structures which could have some of the properties of biological order. These could get stabilised and developed because of their ability of splitting water molecules into hydrogen and oxygen and effecting nitrogen and carbon dioxide fixation. This started a flow of energy through them providing still greater stability²⁷ and enabled these particles to develop and evolve.

Thus, it was not only in the beginning of life that water was selected for splitting, utilising sunlight and producing hydrogen for reduction of inorganic carbon to organic carbon and nitrogen to ammoniacal nitrogen so much needed for the sustenance of life and living forms but even today this ability of splitting water with sunlight is continuing and is providing all the energy needed by the living forms through photosynthesis, where hydrogen is used up for the reduction of inorganic carbon and O₂ is set free in the atmosphere.

The study of the process of life synthesis will not only provide information of how life came into existence; but if studied with functional point of view may also point the way out of the present energy crisis; by emulating the process of utilising solar energy for its conversion to chemical bonds as nature did a few billion years back to initiate the existence of living forms on the earth.

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